

DIGITAL BRAINS: THE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE DRIVEN EVOLUTION OF PHARMACY PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence use in pharmaceutical technology has increased over the years, and the use of technology can save time and money while providing a better understanding of the relationships between different formulations and processes parameters. Artificial intelligence is a branch of computer science that deals with problem-solving by the aid of symbolized programming. It has greatly evolved into a science of problems-solving with the huge applications in business, health care, and engineering. The article describes the drugs discovery, tools of AI, manufacturing execution systems, automated control processes systems, AI to predict new treatment, development of novel peptides from natural foods, treatment and management of rare diseases, drug adherence and dosage, challenges to adoption of AI in

pharma. AI plays an important role in various fields of pharmacy like drug discovery, drug delivery formulation development, poly pharmacology, hospital pharmacy, etc.

1 INTRODUCTION

Alan Turing's seminal work, "Computing Machinery and Intelligence," published in 1950, marked the beginning of the artificial intelligence (AI) debate. In 2004, John McCarthy defined AI as "the science and engineering of making intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs."^[1,2]

Designed by Newell and Simon in 1955, it may be considered the first AI program. The person who finally coined the term artificial intelligence and is regarded as father of AI is

John McCarthy.

When was AI introduced?

- ✓ In 1956, the beginning of AI can be traced to classical philosopher's attempts to describe human thinking as a symbolic system.
- ✓ But the field of AI wasn't formally founded until 1956, at a conference at Dartmouth College, in Hanover, New Hampshire, where the term AI was coined.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a stream of science related to intelligent machine learning, mainly intelligent computer programs, which provides results in the similar way to human attention process.^[3,4]

AI technology is exercised to perform more accurate analyses as well as to attain useful interpretation. The progress and innovation of AI applications are often associated to the fear of unemployment threat. However, almost all advancements in the applications of AI technology are being celebrated on account of the confidence, which enormously contributes its efficacy to the industry.

Recently, AI technology becomes a very fundamental part of industry for the useful applications in many technical and research fields.

The emergent initiative of accepting the applications of AI technology in pharmacy including drug discovery, drug delivery formulation development and other healthcare applications have already been shifted from hype to hope.^[5,6]

The uses of AI models also make possible to predict the *in vivo* responses, pharmacokinetic parameters of the therapeutics, suitable dosing, etc. According to the importance of pharmacokinetic prediction of drugs, the uses of *in silico* models facilitate their effectiveness and inexpensiveness in the drug research.⁸ There are two key classes of AI technology developments.^[7,8]

The first one comprises the conventional computing methodologies including expert systems, which are capable of simulating the human experiences and illustrating the conclusions from the principles, like expert systems. The second one comprises the systems, which can model the mode of brain functioning employing the artificial neural networks (ANNs). In specific, various ANNs like deep neural networks (DNNs) or

recurrent neural networks (RNNs) control the evolutions of AI technology. In Merck Kaggle¹¹ and NIH Tox21 challenge,¹² DNN issues show the greater predictivity than the baseline machine learning methodologies.

The machine learning employs suitable statistical methodologies with the capability to learn with or devoid of being unequivocally programmed.¹³ In addition, de novo design promotes the invention of newer drug molecules with regard to optimal or desired qualities.¹⁴ In the current review article, the uses of AI in pharmacy, especially in drug discovery, drug delivery formulation development, poly pharmacology and hospital pharmacy are discussed.^[9,10]

Figure 1.1: Artificial Intelligence.

2 . HISTORY OF AI

Maturation of AI (1943-1952)

- Year 1943-The first work which is now recognized as AI was done by Warren McCulloch and Walter pits in 1943. They proposed model of artificial neurons.
- Year 1949-Donald Hebb demonstrate an updating rule for modifying the connection strength between neurons. His rule is now called Hebbian learning.
- Year 1950-The Alan Turing who was an English mathematician and pioneered machine learning in 1950. Alan Turing publishes “Computing machinery and intelligence “In which he proposed at a test. The test can check the machine ability to exhibit intelligent behavior equivalent to human intelligence, called a Turing test.

The birth of AI (1952-1956)

- Year 1955-An Allen Newell and Herbert A. Simon created the first artificial intelligence program which was named as “Logic theorist”. This program had proved

38 of 52 mathematics theorems, and find new and more elegant proofs for some theorems.

- Year 1956-The word AI first adopted by American computer scientist John McCarthy at Dartmouth conference. For the first time, AI coined as an academic field.^[11,12]

The golden years-early enthusiasm (1956-1974)

- Year 1966-The researchers emphasized developing algorithms which can solve mathematical problems. Joseph Weizenbaum created the first chatbot in 1966, which was named as ELIZA.
- Year 1972-The first intelligent humanoid robot was built in Japan which was named as WABOT-1.

The first AI winter (1974-1980)

- The duration between years 1974 to 1980 was the first AI winter duration. AI winter refers to the time period where computer scientist dealt with a severe shortage of funding from government for AI researches. During AI winter, an interest of publicity on AI was decreased.^[13]

A boom of AI (1980-1987)

- Year 1980-After AI winter duration, AI came back with “Expert system “. Expert system was programmed that emulate the decision-making ability of human expert. In the year 1980, the first national conference of the American association of AI was held at Stanford University.

The second AI winter (1987-1993)

- The duration between the years 1987 to 1993 was the second AI winter duration Again, investors and government stopped in funding for AI research as due to high cost but not efficient result. The expert system such as XCON was very cost effective.

The emergence of intelligent agents (1993-2011)

- Year 1997-In this year, IBM deep blue beats world chess champion, Gary Kasparov, and became the first computer to beat a world chess champion. Year 2002-for the first time, AI entered the home in the form of Roomba, a vacuum cleaner.
- Year 2006 – AI came in the Business world till the year 2006. Companies like Facebook, Twitter, and Netflix also started using AI Deep learning, big data and artificial general intelligence.

- Year 2011-In the year 2011, IBM's Watson won jeopardy, a quiz show, where it had to solve the complex questions as well as riddles. Watson had proved that it could understand natural language and can solve tricky questions quickly.
- Year 2012 – Google has launched an Android app feature “Google now “, which was able to provide information to the user as a prediction.

Year 2014 – In the year 2014, Chatbot “Eugene Goostman” won a competition in the infamous “Turing test”. Year 2018 – The “Project Debater” from IBM debated on complex topics with two master debaters and also performed extremely well. Google has demonstrated an AI program “Duplex” which a virtual assistant was and which has hairdresser appointment on call, and lady on other side didn't notice that she was talking with the machine.^[14-16] .

Figure 2.1: History or AI.

3. OBJECTIVES OF AI

- **Creation of Expert Systems:** It involves the creation of automated systems that exhibit intelligent behavior and advice humans on the right course of action.
- **Implementation of Human Intelligence in Computers:** It will help create identical cognitive patterns in computers which will help them behave like humans and take appropriate actions to solve complex problems. This will enable automated processes and reduced human workload through the application of algorithms.
- **Multi-Domain Application:** AI will help in multiple domains of implementation like Computer Science, Cognitive Science, Statistics, Psychology, Medical Science, Engineering, Ethics, Natural Sciences, Healthcare, Space Technology, Logic, Linguistics, E-commerce, and more.^[17]

Artificial Intelligence Objectives

Figure 3.1: Artificial Intelligence Objective.

4. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HEALTH CARE

Artificial intelligence in healthcare AI in healthcare has evolved dramatically over the last five decades, leading to significant advancements in a variety of medical fields. The introduction of ML and deep learning (DL) has expanded AI applications, enabling personalized medicine rather than relying solely on algorithms. AI has significantly impacted clinical decision-making, disease diagnosis, as well as clinical, diagnostic, rehabilitative, surgical, and predictive practices. This advancement in AI technology has paved the way for improved diagnostic accuracy, streamlined provider workflow, improved clinical operation efficiency, disease, and therapeutic monitoring, precise procedures, and, ultimately, better patient outcomes.^[18,19]

4.1 Pharmacy practice

Pharmacy practice is an integral part of the healthcare system, which ensures safe and effective medication management and optimized patient care, through various activities such as medication reconciliation, medication review, medication therapy management (MTM), providing drug information, patient education, adverse drug reaction (ADR) monitoring and interprofessional collaborations.^[20]

With rapid advancements in the healthcare sector, the number of prescriptions, complex drug regimens, and administrative tasks has increased noticeably.

As a result, there is an increasing demand for advanced technological solutions that can

assist healthcare professionals in their daily responsibilities and optimize healthcare service delivery.^[21]

The incorporation of AI technologies provides pharmacists with tools and systems that help them make accurate and evidence-based clinical decisions. By using AI algorithms and ML, pharmacists can quickly analyze large amounts of patient data, including medical records, lab results and medication profiles. This allows them to identify potential drug-drug interactions, assess the safety and efficacy of medicines, and make informed recommendations tailored to individual patients.^[22,23]

Figure 4.1: Artificial Intelligence for research in medicine.

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The application of AI in various areas within the field of pharmacy practice has shown promising prospects. However, existing research gaps need to be addressed to harness the complete potential of AI technologies.

The most important aspect is the comprehensive implementation of AI services within existing pharmacy systems and understanding its impact on health and economic outcomes.

In this review, we will be exploring the various AI applications in the field of pharmacy

practice; the research gaps and challenges; and highlighting the future directions for research within the field.^[24-26]

4.2 METHODS

To identify topics of interest for this narrative review, the various databases (PubMed, Google Scholar, and Scopus) were searched for relevant articles.

Various search terms were used to identify the relevant literature, which included “Artificial intelligence,” “Adverse drug reaction,” “ADR,” “Machine learning,” “Deep learning,” “Neural networks,” “Clinical decision support systems,” “Medical Order Entry Systems,” “Computerized Provider Order Entry,” “Pharmacy practice,” “Clinical pharmacy,” “Community pharmacy,” “Hospital pharmacy,” “Pharmacist,” “Medication therapy management,” “Drug dispensing,” “Medical reconciliation,” “Medication adherence,” “Medication optimization,” “Pharmaceutical care,” “Precision medicine.”

The reference list of the relevant articles was also reviewed to identify potentially important papers pertaining to the topic.

Two authors independently conducted the search and the most appropriate ones were included into the review.

AI has been utilized in several studies for ADR prediction and detection. One such study conducted by Mohsen and colleagues, which combined two distinct datasets: drug-induced gene expression profiles from the Open Toxics genomics Project- Genomics Assisted Toxicity Evaluation Systems (TG-GATEs) database and ADR occurrence data from the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) Adverse Events Reporting System (FAERS) database in conjunction with Deep Neural Networks (DNN) for ADR prediction. It includes data filtering and cleaning, feature selection, and hyper parameter tuning.

Decision tree induction, a ML method, was used by Hamman et al. to determine the chemical, physical, and structural properties of compounds that predispose them to cause ADRs. For allergic, renal, CNS, and hepatic ADRs, the models had high predictive accuracies (78.9–90.2%).^[27,28]

In a study by Camia et al., a logistic regression classifier to predict unknown ADRs for

marketed drugs using structural properties of the drug-ADR network as well as chemical and taxonomic properties of drugs as features was developed. Rahman et al. used a random walk algorithm to predict unknown ADRs in a network with drug and ADR nodes, where drug-ADR edges represent known ADRs and drug-drug edges indicate drug target similarity, but they did not validate new ADRs in any real-world clinical data. [14] also created a database of the drug, ADR, and target knowledge and used decision trees and inductive logic programming to predict ADR profiles (rather than individual ADRs), which they validated using FAERS. [29]

Bean et al. created a knowledge graph with four different types of nodes: drugs, protein targets, indications, and adverse reactions. Using this graph, they created a ML algorithm based on a simple enrichment test and demonstrated how well this method performs at classifying known causes of adverse reactions. [30]

Furthermore, other studies involved classifying approved drugs from withdrawn drugs to reduce adverse drug effects, extracting adverse drug events (ADEs) from clinical narratives and automating pharmacovigilance, predicting and preventing adverse drug reactions at an early stage to improve drug safety, identifying medications, adverse drug effects, and their relationships with clinical notes, identifying adverse drug effect symptoms and drugs in clinical notes, detecting adverse drug reactions, and detecting ADES.

Overall, these studies highlight the broad range of AI applications in ADR detection, involving prediction models to clinical decision support tools and knowledge graph-based algorithms. [31-33]

4.3 Clinical decision support system (CDSS)

A clinical decision support system (CDSS) is designed to improve healthcare delivery by supplementing medical decisions with targeted clinical knowledge, patient information, and other health data. Individual patient characteristics are matched to a computerized clinical knowledge base in a CDSS, and patient-specific assessments or recommendations are then presented to the clinician for a decision. This technology enables pharmacists to sift through data and intervene to prevent medication errors, reduce patient complications, and save money. [34,35]

Community Pharmacy Healthcare systems are rapidly transitioning from a single hospital- based care module to a collaborative care system based in the community. Pharmacists can help to improve patient safety and efficacy of pharmacotherapy from the hospital to the community.

The “robotic dispensing system” in the community pharmacies prepares prescribed medicines. It consists of three parts : (1) An automated dispensing robot operated by pharmacy support staff, (2) An automated dispensing robot for powdered medication, and (3) A bar-coded medication dispensing support system with personal digital assistance. ML models also allow e-mails to be personalized faster and more accurately than any human. Chat bots can be used to improve service delivery efficiency.^[36]

Walgreen collaborated with a telehealth company, to develop a video chat platform for patients to interact with healthcare professionals. AI can also help with inventory management, where community pharmacists can predict what their patients will require in the future, stock them, and use personalized software to send e-mails to remind patients of drug requirements.^[37]

A patient’s future drug purchase can be predicted using AI-powered data analytics. The pharmacist will be able to make better stock procurement decisions if AI can predict the patient’s drug purchase.^[38,39]

An AI company, created a software for a German online and catalog retailer, which can predict what the retailer will sell in 30 days with 95% accuracy. This resulted in reduction in delivery schedule for purchased products from one to two days by allowing direct delivery from the supplier to the consumer without passing through the ware house.^[40]

The University of California San Francisco (UCSF) Medical Center also prepares and tracks medications using robotic technology. They claim that the technology has prepared 3,500,000 medication doses without error. The robot has proven to be far superior to humans in terms of both size and ability to deliver accurate medications.

The robotic technology’s capabilities include the preparation of oral and injectable medicines, including toxic chemotherapy drugs. The robotics package, and dispense individual doses of pills.

The machines also assemble the doses onto a bar-coded plastic ring, which contains all medications that a patient must take within 12 h.

The automated system's capabilities include the ability to prepare sterile preparations for chemotherapy as well as fill intravascular syringes with the appropriate medications.^[41]

Figure 4.2: AI Model Development.

4.4 Drug-drug interactions

Drug-drug interactions (DDIs) have been identified as a significant cause of ADRs, which contribute to rising healthcare costs. Predicting DDI necessitates the use of multiple drug characteristics and known DDI. The most used databases are Drug Bank, SIDER, TWO SIDES, Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG), Lex icomp, and Micromedex. Existing DDI computational methods are classified into three types: similarity-based methods, networks-based methods, and ML methods. Van Laree et al. developed an algorithm that predicts QTcB prolongation and issues alerts when DDIs increase the risk of QTcB prolongation.^[42]

Figure 4.3: Drug-Drug Interaction.

Sutu Mei and Kun Zhang proposed a simple f-drug target profile representation to depict drugs and drug pairs, which was used to build an l2-regularized logistic regression model to predict DDIs. Song et al. created a largescale DDI predictor by combining five types of drug similarities: 2D molecular structure similarity, 3D pharmacophores similarity, drug interaction profile similarity, target similarity, and adverse effect similarity, and provided a Polynomial Kernel Support Vector Machines (PK-SVM) classifier to carry out the predictive.^[43]

4.5 MClinical implementation

The lack of empirical evidence proving the efficacy of AI-based interventions in prospective clinical trials is the first barrier to successful implementation.

The majority of AI research in healthcare is generally retrospective, in a controlled environment. As a result, extrapolating results to real-world scenario is difficult.

4.6 Social concerns

One of the major social concerns is the AI in healthcare, will replace jobs, making healthcare workers obsolete. The threat of replacement leads to distrust and opposition to AI-based interventions in the healthcare. This belief, however, is largely based on a misunderstanding of AI in its various forms. Healthcare professionals have generally failed to keep pace with other professionals in terms of incorporating new technologies into their daily work. Previous experiences in healthcare indicate that the simple mentation period is an important stage in the innovation process. In practice, inventing and testing a new AI technology is not enough; other factors that can stymie its implementation in real-world healthcare, such as. (1) the limited data structure and quality in existing electronic health systems, (2) the alteration of the clinician-patient relationship, (3) the difficulties associated with clinical integration and interoperability, must also be considered.^[45]

5. TOOLS OF AI

Robot pharmacy: The objective of improving the safety of patients, UCSF Medical Center uses robotic technology for the preparation and tracking of medications. According to them, the technology has prepared 3, 50, 000 medication doses without any error.

The robot has proved to be far better than humans both in size as well as its ability to deliver Robot pharmacy: The objective of improving the safety of patients, UCSF Medical Center uses robotic technology for the preparation and tracking of medications. According to them, the technology has prepared 3, 50, 000 medication doses without any error.

The robot has proved to be far better than humans both in size as well as its ability to deliver accurate medications. The abilities of the robotic technology include preparation of oral as well as injectable medicines which include chemotherapy drugs that are toxic. This has given freedom to the pharmacists and nurses of UCSF so that they can utilize their expertise by focusing on direct patient care and working with the physicians.^[46]

Med Robot: Med is a short form for medicine and engineering designing intelligence. Tools of Althea pain management robot was developed as part of a project led by Tanya Bearn, professor of Community Health Sciences at the University of Calgary in Alberta. She got the idea after working in hospitals where children scream during medical procedures.

The robot first builds a rapport with the children and then tells them what to expect during a medical procedure although the robot cannot think, plan, or reason, it can be programmed such that it shows to have AI Erica robot: Erica is a new care robot that has been developed in Japan by Hiroshi Ishiguro, a professor at Osaka University.) It was developed in collaboration with the Japan Science and Technology Agency, Kyoto University, and the Advanced Telecommunications Research Institute International (ATR).

It can speak Japanese and has a blend of European and Asian facial feature Like any normal human being, it likes animated films, desire to visit south-east Asia, and wants a life partner who would chat with it.

The robot cannot walk independently; however, it has been developed with the ability to understand and answer questions with human-like facial expressions. Erica is the “most beautiful and intelligent” android as Ishiguro fixed up the features of 30 beautiful women and used the average for designing the robot’s nose, eyes, and so on.^[47]

TUG robots: Aethon TUG robots are designed to autonomously travel through the

hospital and deliver medications, meals, specimens, materials, and haul carry heavy loads such as linen and trash. It has two configurations, i.e., fixed and secured carts as well as exchange base platform that can be used to carry racks, bins, and carts. The fixed carts are used for delivering medications, sensitive materials, and laboratory specimens, whereas, the exchange platform is employed to Vyas, et al.: Artificial Intelligence : New era in pharmacy profession Asian Journal of Pharmaceutics Apr-Jun 2018 transport materials that can be loaded on different racks. The TUG can deliver several types of carts or racks thus making it a very flexible and utilizable resource.^[48]

Automated control process system [ACPS] : The elements of [ACPS] include : Sensing process variables" value. Transmission of signal to measuring element. Measure process variable. Presenting the value of the measured variable. Set the value of the desired variable.

Comparison of desired and measured values. control signal transmission to final control element. and Control of manipulated value. Berg : Berg is Boston-based biotech and is one of the key players employing AI in its various processes.

It has an AI-based platform for drug discovery, which has a huge database of patients and this is used to find as well as validate the various biomarkers responsible for causing diseases and then decides therapies according to the obtained data. The motto of the company is to speed up the process of drug discovery and to bring about a reduction in the cost with the aid of AI as it obliterates guesswork that is involved in the process of drug development.^[49]

6. TECHNOLOGIES USED IN AI

- **Natural language processing (NLP):** program computers to process and analyze large amounts of natural language data.
- **Support vector machine (SVM):** Given a labeled training data (supervised learning), the algorithm outputs an optimal hyperplane which categorizes new examples.
- **Heuristics:** mental shortcuts that ease the cognitive load of decide. Eg., using a rule of thumb, an educated guess, an intuitive judgment, a guesstimate, profiling, or common sense.^[50]
- **Artificial neural networks (ANN):** Started in way back in 1940s, is an information

processing model that is inspired by the way biological nervous systems, such as the brain, process information. An artificial neuron is a mathematical function. ANN takes data samples rather than entire data sets to arrive at solutions, which saves both time and money. ANNs have three layers that are interconnected (PYTHON). Neural networks learn things in exactly the same way as the brain, typically by a feedback process called back-propagation ANNs are used in Self Driving cars, Character Recognition, Image Compression and Stock Market Prediction. Software of artificial neural networks (ANNs) models the pattern recognition capacities of brain neural networks. Like a single neuron in the brain, artificial neuron system receives feedback from many external sources, processes it, and makes decisions Interestingly, ANN simulates the biological nervous system and uses adaptive biological neurons analogues.¹¹ ANN represents a promising modeling technique, especially for data sets having non-linear relationships which are frequently encountered in pharmaceutical processes.

The various applications of ANNs can be summarized into classification or pattern recognition, prediction and modeling (Figure 1). Based on their pattern of association ANNs are classified as supervised 'associating networks, Unsupervised feature-extracting networks and Non-adaptive unsupervised networks.

The potential applications of ANN methodology in the pharmaceutical sciences range from interpretation of analytical data, image recognition, drug and dosage form design through bio pharmacy to clinical pharmacy.^[51,52]

Figure 6.1: Types of AI.

7. CONCLUSION

Artificial intelligence (AI) of health industry is a set of multiple technologies that allow machines to feel, understand, act, and learn to perform administrative and clinical health care functions. In conclusion, the future lies in cooperation between humans and machines, and alongside technological advances, human clinical experts will need to adapt, learn and grow. Although potential experts will have to be both medical and technology experts, it is evolution of medicine, not extinction. There are various AI and machine learning applications in pharmaceutical applications, including disease identification/diagnosis, personalized treatment/behavioural modification, drug discovery/manufacturing, radiology and radiotherapy, smart electronic health records, prediction of epidemic outbreaks, sales, marketing, predictive analytics, and so on. In addition, AI and ML-based analytics are superior for advertising, particularly because success often needs many ongoing complex decisions with a high degree of judgment. Revenue on the AI health sector is projected to hit \$6.6 billion by 2021, a 40% CAGR, and the medical AI industry is expected to expand more than 10 times in only the next five years.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing pharmacy practice by integrating advanced technologies into drug discovery, clinical decision-making, patient care, and pharmaceutical business models. With the power of data analytics, machine learning, and automation, AI is reshaping how pharmacists work and how patients receive care.

Key aspects of this evolution include:

- **Drug Discovery & Development** – AI accelerates identification of new drug molecules, predicts pharmacological activity, and reduces R&D costs.
- **Precision Medicine** – Machine learning enables personalized therapy based on genetics, biomarkers, and patient-specific data.
- **Clinical Decision Support** – AI tools assist pharmacists in identifying drug interactions, optimizing dosing, and improving patient safety.
- **Pharmacy Operations** – Automation in dispensing, inventory management, and supply chain ensures efficiency and error reduction.

- **Patient Engagement** – AI-powered chatbots and mobile apps enhance medication adherence, counseling, and telepharmacy services.
- **Regulatory & Ethical Challenges** – Ensuring data privacy, addressing bias in AI models, and integrating AI responsibly into healthcare systems remain major concerns.

In essence, **AI is transforming pharmacy from a traditional product-centered discipline into a data-driven, patient-centered, and technology-enabled practice**, heralding a new era of innovation and improved healthcare outcomes.

Operationally, AI has optimized **pharmacy workflow** through robotic dispensing, inventory management, and predictive supply chain models, minimizing human error and ensuring continuity of care. This efficiency allows pharmacists to dedicate more time to patient-centered activities rather than administrative tasks.

However, the evolution also presents challenges. Issues of **data privacy, algorithmic transparency, ethical use of patient data, and the potential over-reliance on automated systems** must be carefully addressed. Pharmacists must remain the ultimate decision-makers, ensuring that AI complements—rather than replaces—their professional expertise and human judgment. Additionally, education and training programs must be restructured to prepare future pharmacists to work seamlessly with AI technologies.

Looking ahead, AI's role in pharmacy will continue to expand, integrating with emerging fields such as pharmacogenomics, blockchain, wearable technologies, and augmented reality. The future pharmacist will act not only as a medication expert but also as a **digital health navigator**, capable of bridging human compassion with machine intelligence.

8. REFERENCES

1. Turing AM, "Computing machinery and intelligence." *Mind.*, **1950**; 49: 433–460.
2. McCarthy J, "What is artificial intelligence?", 1997
<http://www.formal.stanford.edu/jmc/whatisai/whatisai.html>
3. Bohr A, Memarzadeh K, "The rise of artificial intelligence in healthcare applications." *Artific Intellig Healthc*, **2020**: 25–60.
4. Davenport T, Kalakota R, "The potential for artificial intelligence in healthcare."

- Future Healthc J*, **2019**; 6: 94–98.
5. Secinaro S, Calandra D, Secinaro A, Muthurangu V, Biancone P, “The role of artificial intelligence in healthcare: a structured literature review.” *BMC Med. Inform Decis. Mak.*, **2021**; 21: 1–23.
 6. Kaul V, Enslin S, Gross SA, “History of artificial intelligence in medicine.” *Gastrointest Endosc*, **2020**; 92: 807–812.
 7. Garcia-Cardenas V, Rossing CV, “Pharmacy practice research—a call to action.” *Res Social Adm. Pharm.*, **2020**; 16: 1602–1608.
 8. Raza MA, Aziz S, Noreen M, “Artificial Intelligence (AI) in pharmacy: an overview of innovations”, *Innov. Pharm.*, 2022.
 9. Manikiran SS, Prasanthi NL, “Artificial intelligence : milestones and role in pharma and healthcare sector.” *Pharm. Times.*, **2019**; 51: 9–56.
 10. Mohsen A, Tripathi LP, Mizuguchi K, “Deep learning prediction of adverse drug reactions in drug discovery using open TG–GATEs and FAERS databases.” *Front Drug Discov.*, **2021**; 1: 768-792.
 11. Celik HT, “An artificial intelligence approach to support detection of neonatal adverse drug reactions based on severity and Probability scores: a new risk score as web-tool.” *Children*, **2022**; 9: 18-26.
 12. Hammann F, Gutmann H, Vogt N, “Prediction of adverse drug reactions using decision tree modeling.” *Clin. Pharmacol Therap.*, **2010**; 88: 52–59.
 13. Cami A, Arnold A, Manzi S, “Predicting adverse drug events using pharmacological network models.” *Sci. Transl. Med.*, **2011**; 3: 114-127.
 14. Rahmani H, Weiss G, Bender A, “ARWAR: a network approach for predicting adverse drug reactions.” *Comput. Biol. Med.*, **2016**; 68: 101–108.
 15. Bresso E, Grisoni R, Marchetti G, “Integrative relational machine-learning for understanding drug side-effect profiles.” *BMC Bioinformatics*, **2013**: 14-20.
 16. Bean DM, Wu H, Iqbal E, “ Knowledge graph prediction of unknown adverse drug reactions and validation in electronic health records.” *Exploratory Research in Clinical and Social Pharmacy*, 2018; 8: 42-84.
 17. Onay A, Onay M, Abul O, “Classification of nervous system withdrawn and approved drugs with Tox Print features via machine learning strategies.” *Comput Methods Programs Biomed.*, **2017**; 142: 9–19.
 18. Dandala B, Joopudi V, Devarakonda M, “Adverse drug events detection in clinical notes by jointly modeling entities and relations using neural networks.” *Drug Saf*,

- 2019**; 42: 135–146.
19. Dey S, Luo H, Fokoue A, Hu J, Zhang P, “Predicting adverse drug reactions through interpretable deep learning framework.” *BMC Bioinform.*, **2018**; 19: 1–3.
 20. Yang X, Bian J, Gong Y, Hogan WR, Wu Y, “MADEx : a system for detecting medications, adverse drug events, and their relations from clinical notes.” *Drug Saf.*, **2019**; 42: 123–133.
 21. Chapman AB, Peterson KS, Alba PR, DuVall SL, Patterson OV, “Detecting adverse drug events with rapidly trained classification models.” *Drug Saf.*, **2019**; 42: 147–156.
 22. Duan L, Khoshneshin M, Street WN, Liu M, “Adverse drug effect detection.” *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform*, **2012**; 17: 305–311.
 23. Huang LC, Wu X, Chen JY, “Predicting adverse side effects of drugs.” *BMC Genomics*, **2011**; 12: 1-5.
 24. Sutton RT, Pincock D, Baumgart DC, “An overview of clinical decision support systems: benefits, risks, and strategies for success.” *NPJ. Digit. Med.*, **2020**; 6: 3-17.
 25. “Artificial Intelligence Applications in education and Pharmacy Practice,” 2023, <https://www.pharmacytimes.com/view/artificial-intelligenc>
 26. Takase T, Masumoto N, Shibatani N, “Evaluating the safety and efficiency of robotic dispensing systems.” *J Pharm. Health Care Sci.*, **2022**; 8: 1-24.
 27. Chatbots, “Medicine Delivery”, 2023, <https://hellotars.com/chatbot-templates/healthcare/Hk8N4h/medicine-ordering-chatbot>
 28. Walgreen, “Convenient virtual care”, 2023, <https://www.walgreens.com/findcare/category/acute-telehealth>
 29. Ahmed S, “How can artificial intelligence help community pharmacists”, 2023, <https://www.chemistanddruggist.co.uk/CD137026/How-can-artificial-intelligence-help-community-pharmacists>
 30. Otto Group, “Otto group solutions”, 2023, <https://www.ottogroup.com/en/about-us/konzern-firmen/Otto-Group-Solution-Provider.php>
 31. UCSF, “Robotic Pharmacy Aims to Improve Patient Safety”, 2023, <https://www.ucsf.edu/news/2011/03/9510/new-ucsf-robotic-pharmacy-aims-improve-patient-safety>
 32. Institute of Medicine, “To Err Is Human : Building a Safer Health System”, Washington National Academy Press., 1999.
 33. Lesar, et al, “Factors related to errors in medication prescribing.” *JAMA*, **1997**; 27:

- 312–317.
34. ungreithmayr V, Meid AD, Haefeli WE, “The impact of a computerized physician order entry system implementation on 20 different criteria of medication documentation a before-and-after study.” *BMC Med. Inform Decis. Mak.*, **2021**; 21: 1–2.
 35. Schiff G, “Brigham and Women’s Hospital, Harvard Medical School, Partners HealthCare”, 2023, <https://www.fda.gov/files/drugs/published/Computerized-Prescriber-Order-Entry-Medication-Safety.pdf>
 36. Johnson M, Patel M, Phipps A, Van der Schaar M, “The potential and pitfalls of artificial intelligence in clinical pharmacology.” *CPT Pharmacometrics Syst Pharmacol*, **2023**; 12: 279–284.
 37. Blasiak Agata, Truong Anh, Jeit Wen, “AI: A prospective feasibility trial to dynamically modulate personalized chemotherapy dose with artificial intelligence.” *J Clin. Oncol*, **2022** 40: 15-74.
 38. Martin JH, Norris R, Barras M, “Therapeutic monitoring of vancomycin in adult patients: a consensus review of the American Society of Health-System Pharmacists, the Infectious Diseases Society of America, and the society of infectious diseases pharmacists.” *Clin. Biochem. Rev.*, **2010**; 31: 21–24.
 - 39 Wang Z, Ong CL, Fu Z, “AI models to assist vancomycin dosage titration. *Front Pharmacol.*” **2022**; 13: 801-928.
 - 40 Hu YH, Tai CT, Tsai CF, Huang MW, “Improvement of adequate digoxin dosage : an application of machine learning approach.” *J Healthc. Eng.*, **2018**; 39: 42-45.
 41. Roche-Lima A, Roman-Santiago A, Feliu-Maldonado R, “Machine learning algorithm for predicting warfarin dose in caribbean hispanics using pharmacogenetic data.” *Front Pharmacol*, **2020**; 10: 15-50.
 42. Han K, Cao P, Wang Y, “A review of approaches for predicting drug–drug interactions based on machine learning.” *Front Pharmacol*, **2022**; 12: 39-66.
 43. Mei S, Zhang K, “A machine learning framework for predicting drug–drug interactions.” *Sci. Rep.*, **2021**; 11: 17-19.
 44. Knox C, Law V, Jewison T, “a comprehensive resource for ‘omics’ research on drugs.” *Nucleic Acids Res.*, **2010**; 39: 1035-1041.
 45. Kuhn M, Campillos M, Letunic I, Jensen LJ, Bork P, “A side effect resource to capture phenotypic effects of drugs.” *Mol. Syst. Biol.*, **2010**; 6: 3-5.
 46. Tatonetti NP, Ye PP, Daneshjou R, Altman RB, “Data-driven prediction of drug effects and interactions.” *Sci. Transl. Med.*, **2012**; 4: 12-31.

47. Kanehisa M, Furumichi M, Tanabe M, Sato Y, Morishima K, “new perspectives on genomes, pathways.” *Disease Drugs Nucleic Acids Res.*, **2017**; 45: 353-361.
48. Drug Information, 2023, <https://www.uptodate.com/contents/table-of-contents/drug-information>
49. Micromedex, 2023, <https://www.micromedexsolutions.com/micromedex2/librarian/deeplinkaccess?institution=31u5n877i33c6a9r5t42a1g1e6n5a210105%5E1466j%5E0f9h23&source=deepLink>
50. Van Laere S, Muylle KM, “Machine learning techniques outperform conventional statistical methods in the prediction of high risk QTc prolongation related to a drug-drug interaction.” *J Med. Syst.*, **2022**; 46: 1-10.
51. Goodfellow, “Generative adversarial nets.” *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2014; 27: 2-7.
52. Satyanarayanan, M, “The emergence of edge computing.” *Computer*, **2017**; 50: 30–39.